

Digital Technology as a Tool for Changing Learning Space for Workers' Training in Nigeria

Funmilola Elizabeth Akinyooye Ph.D

Department of Adult Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Abstract

Workers are essential part of the organisational system because they represent the human capital resources that drive all other factors or parts of the system in a bid to achieve the organizational goal. In order to keep the workers abreast of changes and to ensure acquisition of requisite skills needed for optimal performance, there is always the need to engage the workers in training and retraining from time to time. Organization of trainings for workers come in different forms and types. There could be on the job training where workers are exposed to learning components while on duty at work. There could also be organization of training outside the workplace when workers take time off to undergo trainings which will help in additional skill acquisition. Facilitators used for workers training can either be internal or external facilitators depending on the needs and choice of organisers. However, with the emergence of technology and the recent occurrence like the world pandemic which nearly stopped all activities even at the workplace, there have been many evolutions on how activities at workplace can be carried out. This is also inclusive of training process which can afford the workers the opportunity to learn and improve their skills inspite of the limitations prevalent in the world. One would then think of exploring digital training for workers in Nigeria. This paper looks at the need for a change of learning space for Nigerian workers, opportunities in digital training, challenges of digital technology at the workplace for training and some suggestions on how to maximize the benefits for training Nigerian workers.

Keywords: *Digital Technology, Learning Space, Workers, Training.*

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Introduction

Future learning environments almost certainly involve some form of digital learning, whether it is in the foreground or the background. The potential of ICT is substantial when integrated into a social, economic, and organizational framework that is open to innovation and backed by a supportive policy environment, despite the fact that it is obvious that technology alone, however strong, cannot automatically bring about the essential changes. The necessity of changing the location of learning for Nigerian workers, opportunities for digital training, difficulties associated with using digital

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technology for training at the workplace, and some recommendations for maximizing its advantages for training Nigerian workers. The effects of digital technology, which should allow businesses to enhance business procedures, automate repetitive work, and lower the cost of contacts with suppliers and consumers, enhancing corporate efficiency, which was in line with the submission of Michaels 2018.

A person who performs a specific sort of job or who works in a specific manner is referred to as a worker. It can be skilled or unskilled. The work could be white collar job or blue collar job. Training is the action of teaching workers some particular skills or types of behaviours in relation to their job. It has three types, induction, on the job and off-the-job training. When Digital technology is used, it increases efficiency and lowers overall costs.

Workers must be ready to switch occupations throughout their careers in order to avoid being laid off or taking a lower-paying position. In order to benefit from technology progress in terms of greater work prospects and higher salaries, ICT foundational skills are becoming more and more crucial. Therefore, employees using the new technology will need to be capable of handling challenging, less automatable tasks like problem solving in novel environments. This requires strong reading, math, and problem-solving skills along with ICT-complementary autonomy, coordination, and collaboration skills (OECD, 2015a).

The term "learning spaces" refers to areas where technology is incorporated into the environment in response to various activities. Computers, iPads, interactive whiteboards, workstations, and a variety of other integrated applications of modern technology for educational purposes are all included into these spaces. Digital competence in Safe Environments to enable individual learning, efficient working, and high-quality outputs, online communities must be built around a shared set of rules and behavioral standards. To be a complete and trusted member of any community, one must become familiar with its rules.

According to the infographic below, foundational skills, competences, and character traits are the three "pillars" that make up digital skills, which are 21st century abilities. 'Soft skills' is another name for it, according to the ITU (2018). Digital literacy, often known as ICT literacy, is a subset of foundational knowledge. The term "a combination of behaviours, expertise, know-how, and work habits" is used in the context of digital skills to refer to a variety of character traits, dispositions, and essential understandings. There are three levels of digital skill types: fundamental, intermediate, and advanced

Literature Review

Valeria Cirillo, Lucrezia Fanti, Andrea Mina, and Andrea Ricci (2021) worked on the impact of Industry on the performance of Italian business, they examined how technology affected business performance, paying particular attention to how new technologies connected to the Industry paradigm affected growth in sales, average wages, and labor productivity. The results showed that there was proof of a beneficial influence of new technologies on performance in Italy. Koch et al. (2021) analyze the impact of industrial robots in manufacturing using Spanish data from the ESEE Survey, they discovered that the use of robots increases output by 20% to 25%, lowers labour expenses, and positively influences corporate job growth (at a rate of roughly 10% on average). Researchers Acemoglu et al. (2020) and Domini et al. (2021) examine

the results of French companies' investments in robots. Acemoglu et al. (2020) show how adopting new business models boosts productivity and competitiveness while reducing the labor share and the proportion of manufacturing workers. Domini et al. (2021) also conducted research in France and asserted that the organisation benefitted from the introduction of digital technologies. The same claim was supported by the Spanish research of Koch et al. 2021.

When skills needs are firm-specific or there are greater labor market frictions, according to Ramachandran, 1993, training is the relative more effective answer. Hamermesh and Pfann, 1996 backed up Ramachandran's conclusion. In his paper, According to Raffaelli et al. (2018), training may affect how employees view a new technology and how they feel about change in the challenging cognitive process of adjusting to radical new technologies. The research on ICT adoption and training has produced some interestingly divergent findings. For instance, although Giuri et al. (2008) did not, Arvanitis (2005) did find evidence of complementarity between investments in information technology and training.

Workers Training

A person who performs a specific type of work or who works in a specific manner is referred to as a worker. It may require expertise or not. Work could be classified as white collar or blue collar. Training is the process of imparting to employees specific abilities or mannerisms relevant to their line of work. Induction, on-the-job training, and off-the-job training are its three subtypes. Digital technology is used, which increases efficiency and lowers overall costs. Induction, on-the-job training, and off-the-job training are the three primary categories of training that will be discussed in this paper and are relevant to workers. The first is induction training, which is given to new employees when they start working for a company. Typically, it includes a tour of the workplace's facilities, details on health and safety, specialist training on any jobs or abilities required for the position, information on the organization's regulations, such as those pertaining to holiday pay and absence procedures, and an introduction to coworkers. On-the-job training, on the other hand, is instruction you receive at your job. Numerous on-the-job training programs are available for businesses to use, including: Coaching, role-playing, work rotation, shadowing, and demonstration which are the five subtypes of on-the-job training. During coaching, a knowledgeable staff member will demonstrate a task to a worker step-by-step. The more experienced employee, or "coach," will help the employee as they develop by transmitting their expertise and skills. A scenario is performed out through role play to see how an employee would respond in a specific circumstance. This will allow the individual to practice appropriate reactions to situations that might occur at work. The usage of job rotation allows staff workers to experience a range of jobs inside the company, allowing them to pick up new skills from each department or job function. By "shadowing" another employee, an employee can see them at work and gain a better understanding of how they carry out their responsibilities. Typically, this is for a set period of time, such as a few days. Demonstrators are employees who see a task or a particular process being accomplished and then perform the task or process themselves. Thirdly, off-the-job training is instruction received while not at work. This training can be held in a variety of other locations, such as colleges or training centers. Colleges, which are recognized educational institutions, allow staff members to enroll in a certain course. This could be done through distance learning, day release, or evening classes. An area designed specifically for training is referred to as a training

center. Employees could be directed to training facilities for the acquisition of new skills. These different forms of training process have yielded results while some may not really have the desired effects. Factors responsible for not achieving training objectives may vary. That is why it is necessary to conduct an evaluation to determine the extent to which the objectives set out initially have been achieved and also consider some other platforms which can afford the Nigerian workers opportunities which are not available with physical trainings. One may then wonder if the change in the learning space for these workers using digital technology could afford them achievements of the set out objectives in training.

Digital Technology for Workers Training

The phrase "digital technology" describes a broad range of instruments, services, technologies, and applications that make use of various hardware and software. It has been described as a field of engineering or science that focuses on developing and utilizing digital computerized tools, processes, or systems. (Akinyooye, 2021). These technological tools are intended to facilitate the provision of services and the accomplishment of activities requiring the production, storage, processing, transmission, and presentation of information. Mobile phones, laptops, tablets, digital televisions, radios, robots, webinars, video conferencing, teleconferencing, distance learning, mobile learning, e-learning, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), and blended learning are just a few of the many technologies that previous researchers have proposed. Other examples of digital training platforms for workers include Webinars, digital video- based scenarios and learning management system

The term "learning spaces" refers to areas where technology is incorporated into the environment in response to various activities. A good learning space has three dimensions: the physical environment, the pedagogical elements, and the technical and digital components According to Wall, G. (2016). Learning environments demand familiarity with the fundamental tools and guidelines of online communication. Effective connection requires an understanding of social norms for online contexts, and each learner may hone these abilities via practice and rich contact with other individuals and communities. Additionally, written communication skills are crucial, and their development is aided by active involvement in these forums. It is important to keep in mind that connecting learners and experts also takes place in real-world contexts since learning environments are not just restricted to online settings. As a result, connecting spaces provide entry points for individuals with little computer proficiency to engage in ICT-enabled learning with the help of others and start developing their essential digital skills.

Importance of Using Digital Technology for workers Training

Digital technology platforms for workers' training offer many opportunities for workers, the industry and the society at large. It helps to overcome the shortcomings in the physical learning space used for trainings in the industry. Workers are able to undergo training without fixated time or location. The availability of digital learning resources encourages self-directed skill acquisition, while connections with others provide formal and/or informal guidance and support as needed to develop digital competences. It enables the company to undergo positive changes which comes readily with improved skills acquisition as result of frequent and efficient training

opportunities. It is a comprehensive process that necessitates the participation of staff members in training. Meeting digital customers where they are in need leads to reengineering of business processes, whether they are in the manufacturing or service context. It is crucial in workplaces where employees are receiving training to take advantage of recent innovations like cloud computing. Creating content is essential.

Opportunities to Workers

Opportunities must be seized while they are still futuristic in order to save money and time and reorganize the learning environment. It works best when there is flexibility in the amount of instructor-student engagement time. Workers or learners have the chance to work together with classmates as they disseminate their expertise to a larger global audience (Pinto & Leite, 2020). It provides a means for student autonomy in the classroom. By providing students with a platform where they may access a wealth of educational resources and encourage their own study, the educational process has become more efficient. According to (Pedro, Barbosa & Santos, 2018), digital technology aids in the accomplishment of Goal 4 of the Sustainable Development Agenda (SDG 4) which strives to guarantee that everyone has access to high-quality, inclusive, and egalitarian education and to promote opportunities for lifelong learning. A technology such as this kind has shown to be fantastic for usage by employees due to its outstanding potential to reduce costs over the long term.

Challenges of Digital Technology as Training Platforms for Workers

High Cost and Lack of Motivation

The lack of a systematic approach to teaching and learning, the socioeconomic environment, knowledge of and attitudes toward digital technologies, administrative and technical support, staff development in both teaching and support, and a lack of familiarity with digital technology are all factors that contribute to a lack of motivation to the use of digital technology for training workers. Employees who want to use digital platforms must get acquainted with the skills of navigating through the available channels in order to maximize the opportunities embedded in the use of such digital platforms. The trainers or facilitators should also develop a systemic approach to training using these platforms to increase the motivation levels of their targeted trainees.

Digital Security

The problem's four main facets, economic and social, technological, national and international, and law enforcement have been identified. Social and economic activities are vulnerable to a number of risks. Due to the limited control they have on the design of the software or hardware that is available for purchase in the market, individuals and small enterprises might not be able to determine whether the absence of a specific digital security measure or choice results in an increased risk. (OECD, 2015d: 38-40)

Attitude and Perception of Workers to Training

Some workers' attitudes and perceptions towards the acquisition of digital skills are not encouraging. Some employees believe that their prior experience has been

overshadowed. Some adults are indifferent about change or new innovations and feel at ease with their lack of digital literacy.

Inadequate Digital Competency

The competency to use the tools effectively is lacking or inadequate.

Conclusion

It is necessary for all stakeholders to collaborate in order to jointly develop solutions.

As recommended in the Security Risk Recommendation, Governments ought to take the initiative in promoting the use of digital security risk management by creating national strategies in cooperation with other stakeholders.

Plans and policies should be supported by operational and functional procedures as well as technical leadership at the policy-making levels.

Government and industries should conduct a long-term review of the digital education programs included in the curricula of all professions.

The length of the follow-up period for different digital learning modalities should be standardized, and postponed assessment may be used to gauge knowledge retention.

In circumstances where it is practical, to improve learners' experiences, it is beneficial to include data analytics into assessment and monitoring programs.

Industries should invest in research to determine the best ways to employ digital technology and which skills are best taught in "pure" digital formats as opposed to hybrid learning environments. Management, workers and all stakeholders should make conscious efforts at developing appropriate ICT skills which can help in the effective adoption of digital technology as a platform for training workers. These include general ICT skills required for using technology for work-related purposes, specialized skills required for programming, developing applications, and managing networks, as well as ICT supplemental skills required to carry out new tasks related to the use of ICT, such as information processing, self-direction, problem solving, and communication.

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